

Project:
NANOFACTS
 Grant Agreement (GA) No. 952259

“NETWORKING ACTIVITIES FOR NANOTECHNOLOGY-FACILITATED CANCER THERANOSTICS”

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D5.1: Delivered trainings on research management and administration skills in the first year

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1.2. 23.12.2021.	Added screenshots and conclusion (Mila Djisalov, Dr. Ivana Gadjanski)
1.3 28.12.2021.	Added information about public procurement workshop
1.4. 29.12.2021.	Added additional screenshots and final corrections (Dr. Nikola Knežević)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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1. Introduction

The main goal of the NANOFACTS project is to improve the research excellence at the Biosense Institute in the field of nanomaterial development for use in cancer therapy, imaging and diagnosis, as well as strengthening the capacity of biosensor technologies at the BioSense Institute by developing research in the field of biosensors for cancer detection. One of the main aspects of improving overall research excellence is strengthening the research management and administration (RMA) skills, starting from the initial stages of project preparation when project writing skills are necessary, as well as networking and collaboration when forming a new consortium, and further on to the stage of actual project implementation i.e. management of the funded project that includes processes such as public procurement that may sometimes be challenging to young researchers without prior experience in such activities.

In order to enable Biosense researchers to achieve practical experience in the abovementioned RMA activities, NANOFACTS provides the trainings for all the phases of research project preparation and implementation, including the phase of potential technology transfer that requires the researchers to switch their roles from purely research-oriented towards entrepreneurial and commercial aspects. In this deliverable we focus on the trainings organized from the start of the project until December 31st, 2021. These trainings were dedicated to the project proposal writing, early steps in project planning, management, and collaboration, on best practices for getting the research published, all in the context of the Horizon Europe funding scheme, as the most relevant for the researchers from Biosense Institute, as well as on the process of public procurement in Serbia, which is of high relevance for all Biosense researchers.

2. Trainings

One of the main goals of our activities within Work Package 5 implies the organisation of specific internal trainings for all Biosense (BIOS) researchers. This project's year was focused on different pieces of trainings/events where BIOS researchers had the opportunity to learn about Project writing skills, Public procurement, Project Management, etc. This training provided them knowledge and proficiency that enabled them to raise awareness about guidelines, documentations, principles, and objectives which will help them to conduct their research.

Due to the on-going COVID19 pandemic, all the trainings described in this deliverable were done in the online format, as webinars.

2.1 Best Practices to Get Published

Full title of the webinar: IEEE Authorship and Open Access Symposium for Europe and the Middle East: Best Practises to Get Published to Increase the Exposure and Impact of Your Research.

The IEEE Authorship and Open Access Symposium took place online as a live-streamed event on the 29th of September 2021. This live webinar provided attendees with best practices in preparing a manuscript, navigating the journal submission process, and important tips to help an author get

published. It also reviewed the opportunities for authors to enhance the visibility and impact of their research by publishing in the many open access options available from IEEE. Each informative session featured the perspective of Professor Josep Guerrero from Aalborg University in Denmark, who is a distinguished author and editor. Dr. Guerrero provided critical insights on IEEE's peer review and submission processes and provided tips on what editors look for in submissions.

This webinar was an excellent platform for our young researchers to gain first-hand experience and broaden their knowledge with complete information about the rules and procedures in the publishing process, as well as their ability to choose the proper journal to increase the impact of the research and have the research results visible to the wide scientific audience.

2.1.1 Objectives

- How to increase the visibility and impact of your research
- Tips and best practises to improve author's chances of getting published
- What editors and reviewers look for in submissions
- Common reasons why papers are rejected
- Selecting the right publication for your research submission
- Reasons to consider an open access journal for your submission
- Open access options available from IEEE for authors and institutions
- Research strategies using IEEE Xplore Digital Library
- Authorship tools available from IEEE for promoting open science
- Live Q&A: Ask the experts

2.1.2 Venues

Due to the COVID19 situation, the webinar was held online on the 29th of September, 2021 at 3 PM CEST.

Links:

- https://event.on24.com/wcc/r/3393419/201C9B3BFB967D9B9AE4BF9AFE8CE286?partner_ref=LG_EC_9.2021_RFW_OA_Authorship_Webinar_for_Europe_ME_Clarivate
- <https://ccstatic.ccindex.cn/event/33/93/41/9/rt/1/documents/resourceList163286012071/ieeeopenaccesswebinarslidesforeuropeandmeseptember202131632870136397.pdf>

2.1.3 Materials

Presentations at the webinar were prepared by Professor Dr. Saifur Rahman (Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, United States), Eszter Lukács (Client Services Manager, IEEE), and Judy Brady (Area Manager, Europe IEEE) (**Figure 1**).

Before the training, NANOFACTS's coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević sent the invitation for the webinar to all the NANOFACTS and BIOS researchers via email. After the training, the presentation of the webinar was forwarded to all participants. The webinar was attended by 6 Biosense's researchers who were then awarded a certificate: Dr. Ivana Gadjanski, Dr. Nikola Knežević, Nejra Omerović, Ivana Podunavac, Mirjana Mundžić, and Minja Mladenović.

A Few Quick Notes Before We Get Started

Please note – There is no dial-in number for attendees of this event; please make sure your computer speakers or headset are turned on and the volume is up so that you can hear our presenters.

- Technical Support**
Click the yellow ? icon at the bottom of your screen to see answers to common technical issues or type your issue into the Q&A window.
- Questions for the Presenters**
Type your questions into the Q&A window. Our presenters will answer as many questions as possible during our time together.
- Certificate of Participation**
Remember to click the Certificate icon at the bottom of your screen to request your Certificate of Participation.
- Access to the recording of today's virtual event** will be available a few hours after the webinar is completed. A link to the on-demand version will be emailed to all registered attendees.

Resource List

Click the green icon at the bottom of your screen to download a PDF version of the presentation

Costs associated with specific publishing options

IEEE provides many options for authors to publish as we strive to support the needs of all authors and readers globally.

Although IEEE offers many options to publish at no cost to the author, many authors do opt for certain fee-based offerings listed below which include:

- Article processing charges to support open access publishing options for most titles
- Option to exceed page limits
- Option to print graphics in color

Note: the online publication of graphics in color is **always free**

Options to avoid any page length or color fees

All fees help IEEE to maintain a quality publishing that is financially sustainable, produces the highest quality information possible, and ensures the information is easily discoverable in a robust and reliable digital platform.

IEEE Author Center
Resources & Tools for Authors

Open Access
Your research funder may require that you publish open access, or you may simply want to increase your audience by making your article freely available to read. IEEE offers several open access options to meet your needs. Learn more about our open access publishing options: [IEEE Open Access Publishing Options](#)

Page Length
IEEE offers several options for exceeding page limits, including: [IEEE Open Access Publishing Options](#)

Color Printing
Online publication of your graphics in color is always free at IEEE. You may choose to also print your graphics in color by paying a color page charge. This cost may vary by journal. If you choose to exceed the page limit, you will receive an invoice before article publication.

Most choose IEEE Access for IEEE OA Options

Corresponding author data, 2020 IEEE Journals

Category	Count	Percentage
IEEE Access	2,897	70%
Other	1,213	30%

Why?

- Outstanding editorial resources (over 1,500 expert associate editors and reviewers)
- Speedy submission-to-publication time (~6 weeks)
- Excellent citations and impact factor for a multidisciplinary journal
- Geographically and topically diverse

Publish graphical abstract and share it via Xplore on social media

Published in: IEEE Access (Volume: 9)

Page(s): 44647 - 44670 DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3054730

Date of Publication: 26 January 2021 Publisher: IEEE

Electronic ISSN: 2169-3536 Funding Agency:

The Systematic Mapping results of Software Product Quality Metrics-related 70 articles and conference papers for the 2009 and 2019 years are presented. The mind map presents the knowledge about this area, issues determined to be open to development in this area, and conformity between the papers and internationally valid quality models. View less

Figure 1 Screenshots of the “Best Practices to Get Published” webinar

2.2 The first and final steps in Horizon Europe proposal writing

Full title of the webinar: The first and final steps in Horizon Europe proposal writing – Expert Insights

Searching and exploiting the key sources of funding for a research project, as well as writing proposals addressing different calls for funding, are some of the challenges that all scientists face. Horizon Europe is one of the most demanding funding programs, both due to the high competitiveness as well as to the exact structure of the project application documentation that needs to be followed. For example the proposal templates have specific sections that need to be addressed with high consideration and expertise, covering all the expected factors and outcomes.

The proposal needs to be planned well and the proposal draft should be thoroughly checked. Not all researchers are aware of all the details they should be paying attention on. In this webinar held on the 22nd of October, Ms. Gabriella Lovász, Managing Director of Europa Media, shared her ideas and tips on the process, based on experience she had with clients of Europa Media Non-profit Ltd, that is a Budapest-based company delivering science communication and IT services mainly related to EU projects.

2.2.1 Objectives

- What is Europa Media and how it helps in preparation of EU funded projects
- Introduction to general information
- Participants: researchers involved in the proposal
- From project to impact - strategic planning and programming
- Audience - Quadruple helix – who needs what?
- What are the three key sections of Writing the proposal?
- Quality and efficiency of the implementation
- Project reporting
- Dissemination and Communication activities
- Q&A session

2.2.2 Venues

The webinar about “The first and final steps in Horizon Europe proposal writing” held by Managing Director of Europa Media, Gabriella Lovász was held on October 22nd at 2 PM, online.

Link:

- https://www.emdesk.com/academy/webinar-horizon-europe-proposal-writing?utm_source=follow-up&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=webinar&utm_content=FirstFinalStepsInHorizonEuropeProposalWriting&no-registerwall=1

2.2.3 Materials

Before the webinar, NANOFACTS’s coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević sent an invitation for the webinar to the NANOFACTS project team from Biosense via email. Presentation was prepared by Gabriella Lovász, Managing Director of Europa Media (**Figure 2**).

After the training, the presentation from the webinar was forwarded to all participants. Additionally, Dr. Nikola Knezevic sent a link to access the recording of the webinar to researchers who were not able to listen to it live.

Part A

2. Participants

- Administrative data
- Researchers involved in the proposal
- Role of participating organization in the project
- Up to 5 relevant publications, dataset, goods, etc.
- Up to 5 relevant projects or activities
- Description of any significant infrastructure
- Gender Equality Plan

Allocate adequate attention – ALL partners

Europa Media/EMDESK webinar

3.2 Capacity of participants and consortium as a v (3p)

Describe the consortium. How does it match the project's objectives, and bring together the necessary **disciplinary** and **inter-disciplinary knowledge**. Show how this includes expertise in social sciences and humanities, open science practices, and gender aspects of R&I, as appropriate. Include in the description affiliated entities and associated partners, if any.

Show how the partners will have access to critical infrastructure needed to carry out the project activities. Describe how the members **complement one another** (and cover the value chain, where appropriate). In what way does each of them contribute to the project? Show that each has a valid role, and adequate resources in the project to fulfil that role.

If applicable, describe the industrial/commercial involvement in the project to ensure exploitation of the results and explain why this is consistent with and will help to achieve the specific measures which are proposed for exploitation of the results of the project (see section 2.2).

Other countries and international organisations: If one or more of the participants requesting EU funding is based in a country or is an international organisation that is not automatically eligible for such funding (entities from Member States of the EU, from Associated Countries and from one of the countries in the exhaustive list included in the Work Programme General Annexes B are automatically eligible for EU funding), explain why the participation of the entity in question is essential to successfully carry out the project.

NEW!

Part B

THREE KEY SECTIONS:

1. Excellence (19p)
2. Impact (9p)
3. Quality and Efficiency of the Implementation (17p)

THREE MORE (OPTIONAL) SECTIONS:

1. Financial support to third parties
2. Clinical trials
3. Calls flagged as security sensitive

$$19+9+17 = 45$$

Pathway to impact

Outcome: Successful deployment of existing scientific knowledge and more bio-based solutions introduced in rural areas

Reporting: Results Ownership List new in Horizon Europe

Table 3.2 Results ownership List

Results or other intellectual property of the Hub members	Member country of residence based	Will the ownership of the result be retained by the result owner (i.e. the Hub member) or other consortium member(s) (if any) as a compulsory obligation under the contract?	Contract, in which case will the result be made available to other consortium member(s) (if any) as a compulsory obligation under the contract?	Does the exploitation of the results require access to background of one or several consortium member(s) (if any) as a compulsory obligation under the contract?	Does the exploitation of the results require access to third party IP (if any) as a compulsory obligation under the contract?
Entity: Chip design solution with program code and other software a best practice for some address security, and an identifier such as IOT number	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No

New obligation under HE, it was identified as being an obstacle for the uptake of research results

Figure 2 Screenshots of the “The first and final steps in Horizon Europe proposal writing” webinar

2.3 Learn how to master project planning, management, and collaboration in Horizon Europe

Full title of the live demo/training: Learn how to master project planning, management, and collaboration in Horizon Europe with EMDESK

In order to improve their research management and administration skills, scientists need to know how to go from the initial stages of project preparation (writing and networking and collaborating when forming a new consortium) to the actual project implementation phase, i.e., managing a funded project. In order to get familiar with the existing options, Biosense researchers participated in a Live Demo, organized 29th of October by EMDESK, with the title: Learn how to master project planning, management, and collaboration in Horizon Europe.

2.3.1 Objectives

- To get familiar with EMDESK software opportunities for project planning, management, and collaboration
- Execute, Report & Track features
- Collaborate & Communicate features
- Write & Review features
- Practical example of the EMDESK software (product demo)
- Q&A

2.3.2 Venues

The live demo with the title “Learn how to master project planning, management, and collaboration in Horizon Europe” organized by EMDESK was held on October 29th at 11 AM, online.

- **Link:**
https://www.emdesk.com/product/demo?utm_source=newsletter&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=LiveDemo&utm_content=29.10.EMDESKoverview&scroll=webinar

2.3.3 Materials

Before the live demo/training, NANOFACTS’s coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević sent an invitation for the webinar to the project team from Biosense via email.

Collaborate & Communicate

Coordinating large projects requires more than regular status meetings. EMDESK contextualises collaboration, tying information to project objectives and improving result quality. Optimize the flow of information, eliminate redundant email exchange and increase productivity by collaborating, sharing and having discussions in real-time with intuitive interfaces and integrated communication features.

Access Control

Maintain user and group permissions for each single item

Version Control

Keep, roll-back and restore previous document versions

Audit logs

Easily recapture actions and undo changes

Notifications

Keep users informed with regular and real-time notifications

Execute, Report & Track

Write & Review

Work / Review Status

See all changes since your last visit at a glance, approve and finalize them, or start a discussion

Change Tracking

Use the revision history to see changes, sorted by date and who made the change

Share or Download to Word

Share and publish your document online for instant review. Or save your documents as MS Word

Audit Log

Easily re-capture the entire history of changes and action

Engage in Comments

Bring experts or reviewers into your document by tagging them in the file

Consistent Style

Take control of your document design. Easily format text, paragraphs, tables and images throughout the entire document

Documents are always up-to-date

Create documents with embed data-driven tables and charts that auto-update with the latest project data. It has never been easier to build your own progress and financial reports with one click.

Write & Review

Work / Review Status

See all changes since your last visit at a glance, approve and finalize them, or start a discussion

Change Tracking

Use the revision history to see changes, sorted by date and who made the change

Share or Download to Word

Share and publish your document online for instant review. Or save your documents as MS Word

Audit Log

Easily re-capture the entire history of changes and action

Engage in Comments

Bring experts or reviewers into your document by tagging them in the file

Consistent Style

Take control of your document design. Easily format text, paragraphs, tables and images throughout the entire document

Figure 3 Screenshots of the “Learn how to master project planning, management, and collaboration in Horizon Europe” live demo

2.4 Info session on Horizon Results Booster

Full title of the the info session: Info session on Horizon Results Booster: Bringing a continual stream of innovation to the market and beyond

On October the 5th, Biosense researchers participated in the info session, organized by the European Commission, with the full title: “Info session on Horizon Results Booster: Bringing a continual stream of innovation to the market and beyond”.

The Info session contained five presentations, followed by five testimonials. The presentations were given by 4 speakers: Ms. Alessia Melasecche Germini (META Group); Mr. Nicholas Ferguson (TRUST-IT); Ms. Andrea Di Anselmo (META Group) & Ms. Chiara Eleonora de Marco (Ciaotech/PNO Consulting). Testimonials were given by representatives of different Horizon projects. Full agenda from the info session is shown at **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 Agenda from the Info session on Horizon Results Booster

2.4.1 Objectives

- To learn about the most important rules for Horizon Results Booster
- To learn about Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy
- Assisting projects to improve their existing exploitation strategy
- To learn main support types in “Go-to-Market Support”
- Direct interaction of participants with the speakers (Q&A session)

2.4.2 Venues

The info session on on Horizon Results Booster, organized by European Commission was held on October 5th at 10 AM, online, using Zoom platform.

2.4.3 Materials

Before Info session, NANOFACTS's coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević sent the invitation via email. After the session, the presentation of the webinar was forwarded to all participants via email. Moreover, Dr. Nikola Knezevic sent a link to access the recording of the webinar to researchers who were not able to participate.

During the webinar, our researchers were able to learn from experts in the field. Some screenshots from the session were listed below (**Figure 5**).

YouTube live stream

Service eligibility and requirements

Service 1 - Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy (PDES)	
Module A: Identification and creation of the portfolio of R&I project results	Application is open to both individual projects and project groups (PGs).
Module B: Portfolio Dissemination Plan (design and execution)	Application is open only to PGs. PGs that applied also to PDES-A can be enlarged before starting PDES-B. A portfolio of results has to be provided at the application stage.

↓ Services flow ↓

Service 1 - Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy (PDES)	
Module C: Assisting projects to improve their existing exploitation strategy	Application is open only to single projects. Upload of exploitation plan is optional. Focus is on 3 Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
Service 2 - Business Plan Development (BPD)	
Application is open only to single projects. Focus is only on 1 KER. An Exploitation Plan should be available/Draft Business Plan.	
Service 3 - Go-To-Market Support (G2M)	
6 different support typologies are available. Some of them are only for individual projects. Not all support typologies can be selected (max # of EWDs per project). A (draft) Business Plan should be available. Focus is only on 1 KER.	

Dissemination services and exploitation services **can run in parallel** and have **different experts' teams** delivering them.

CLEANKER Primary project objectives

The ultimate objective of CLEANKER is advancing the integrated Calcium-looping process for CO2 capture in cement plants.

This fundamental objective will be achieved by pursuing the following primary targets:

- Demonstrate the integrated CaL process at TRL 7, in a new demo system connected to the operating cement burning line of the Vernasca 1.300.000 ton/y cement plant, operated by BUZZI in Italy.
- Demonstrate the technical-economic feasibility of the integrated CaL process in retrofitted large scale cement plants through process modelling and scale-up study.
- Demonstrate the storage of the CO2 captured from the CaL demo system, through mineralization of inorganic material in a pilot reactor of 100 litres to be built in Vernasca, next to the CaL demo system.

Info Session on the Horizon Results Booster

HRB for CLEANKER project - CLEAN clinker production by Calcium Looping process

prepared by Martina Fantini – CLEANKER project for Horizon Results Booster

date 05.10.2021

HORIZON RESULTS BOOSTER

Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy (PDES)

Nicholas Ferguson, Trust-IT Services
 Testimonial: Kevin Mallin, GeoDrill project for Horizon Results Booster

05.10.2021

An initiative of the European Commission

Nicholas Ferguson

Benefits of joint dissemination

Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers. By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general.

- Meet the needs of the EC: **Clustering** of projects on commonalities and the **re-use** of results are a key feature of EC policy and Horizon Europe
- **Share** knowledge, expand network and increase opportunities for collaboration
- **Leverage** each projects' networks, communication channels and expertise.
- **Activate** dissemination activities or channels where you are having difficult making an impact
- **Bring** together results of initiatives to create a results portfolio with alternative and complementary results.
- **Broaden** the target communities or networks and boost your project's outreach.
- **Co-organise** of online/offline events or outputs to leverage cross-pollination and collectively showcase outcomes and results.

HRB Modules A and B can give you the right level of support to deliver joint actions which can impact on your own project's outputs

Nicholas Ferguson

HRB in practice with Kevin Mallin, GEODrill - Module B

Delivered to date

- Joint plan
- Group logo & pay off
- Branded flier & video pill

Ongoing in October & November

- Joint workshop at the World Geothermal Congress 2020
- Joint policy brief highlighting the importance of geothermal energy in the context of Green policy
- Dissemination capacity building

This is the only cluster showcasing its joint dissemination of complementary innovations at the World Geothermal congress

Kevin Mallin

Logo and pay off

Video brief

Joint flier

WORLD GEOTHERMAL CONGRESS 2020 REYKJAVIK

Policy Brief

Figure 5 Screenshots from the info session on Horizon Results Booster

2.5 Procurement Challenges in the New Legislative Framework

Full title of the workshop: Procurement Challenges in the New Legislative Framework

Date and time: 27.12.2021. at 09 AM CET

Based on the provisions of the Serbian Public Procurement Act of 2019, which came into power in 2020, all public procurement procedures in Serbia are by legal mandate electronic. The country has established a government Portal for this purpose which covers: Public Procurement Plans, notifications for economic operators, Solicitation and Tender Documents, electronic bids submission, automatic encryption and opening of bids, automatic calculations of numerical elements of bids and comparison analysis, award decisions, E-catalogues, Framework agreements, E-auctions, Dynamic Purchasing Systems, and partially, electronic procedural disputes.

Dynamic Purchasing Systems were also introduced as a technique utilized in qualifying suppliers and awarding public procurements, for cases when it is preferable to have a more flexible and longer term system of purchasing from several sources or in cases of non-fixed quantities are required, instead of a classic contract with one supplier for a fixed quantity for a particular subject matter of procurement. It is in that sense very similar to Framework Agreement as it represents an option and not an obligation for the buyer until a call-off is issued. The call-off is an obligation for both the buyer and the supplier. The differences between a Framework Agreement (FA) and a Dynamic Purchasing System (DPS) are:

- A DPS is open for new suppliers throughout its duration, whereas a FA is closed for entry after it is set up
- A DPS can last longer than an FA (longer than 4 years)
- A DPS must be fully electronic, an FA does not
- Procedural complaints in a DPS do not halt the contract (call-off) award, whereas in an FA it does
- Competition for call-offs in a DPS must last a minimum of 10 days, while in a FA they can be shorter

Conditions for exemption from applying the Public Procurement Act for research and development services was presented, as well as the process and outcome of the public procurement planning conducted at BioSense for 2022.

2.5.1 Objectives

The main objectives covered in the webinar were:

- E-procurement,
- Dynamic Purchasing Systems,
- Exemptions for Research and Development and
- presentation of the Public Procurement Plan of the Institute for 2022

2.5.2 Venues

Considering COVID-19 restrictions, the webinar was held online on the 28th of December 2021 at 9 AM CET via JITSI platform.

The used link: <https://meet.jit.si/BioSenseTipewqKQfxS8rMq8CrDh8mtSA4nvwXfxRF>

2.5.3 Materials

The following pictures present slides used during the workshop:

1

Agenda

1. E-procurement
2. Dynamic Purchasing Systems
3. Exemptions for Research and Development
4. Presentation of the Public Procurement Plan for 2022
5. Q&A and Examples

2

E-procurement (<https://jnportal.ujn.gov.rs>)

The screenshot shows the 'PUBLIC PROCUREMENT' portal interface. At the top, there are four main sections with statistics:

- NOTICES:** Today: 18, Last 7 days: 2,527, 2021: 105,150
- PROCEDURES:** Published today: 4, In the submission deadline: 1,389, 2021: 42,174
- DECISIONS:** Contract awards - 13 days: 2,202, Discontinuation - 13 days: 310, Conclusion of PAK - 10 days: 296
- PROCUREMENT PLANS:** 2022 items amendments Today: 93, Published plans - 7 days: 174

Below these are several news items and announcements:

- Welcome to the Public Procurement Portal:** Public Procurement Portal is developed for the purpose of application of the new Public Procurement Law. Before applying the new Law by using Portal, we suggest you read:
 - Instructions for the users of the new Public Procurement Portal
 - Recently asked questions
- Version 1.10:** Starting from 09.12.2021, version 1.10 of the Public Procurement Portal is available. Version 1.10 includes new features and enhancements listed on the following link.
- Guidelines for the application of the negotiated procedure without publication of contract notice:** Guidelines for the application of the negotiated procedure without publication of contract notice are published on the internet site of the Public Procurement Office. [Link to access the guidelines](#)
- Guidelines for preparation of tender documents and e-tender:** Guidelines for preparation of tender documents and e-tender on the Public Procurement Portal are published on the internet site of the Public Procurement Office. [Link to access the guidelines](#)

At the bottom, there is a section for 'Information about updates of the Portal' and 'Video tutorials'. A video player is visible with the title 'Registracija na Portalu'.

E-procurement

From July 1, 2020, all public procurement procedures in Serbia are electronic (legally mandated use of the government Public Procurement Portal)

What is covered on the Portal:

- Public Procurement Plans are published and searchable, with notification for economic operators freely available
- Solicitation and Tender Documents are freely available
- Submitting electronic Bids
- Automatic encryption and opening of bids
- Automatic calculations of numerical elements of bids and comparison analysis
- Award decisions freely available with searchable metadata
- E-catalogues
- Framework agreements with several suppliers must be done through the Portal
- E-auctions
- Dynamic Purchasing Systems introduced
- Electronic complaints (partly*) (procedural disputes)

What is not covered on the Portal:

- Non-public procurements
- Contract execution (e-contracts, e-invoice)
- Framework agreements with one supplier (Framework Contracts)
- Complaints (procedural disputes) can still be made non-electronically*

Procurement Preparation (BioSense)

Procurement Request Form - Requester View

The screenshot shows the 'Novi zahtev za nabavku' (New procurement request) form in the BioSense system. The form includes fields for:

- Predmet nabavke:** Subject-matter
- Vrsta predmeta:** Classification (list)
- Datum:** Date
- Detaljan opis:** Detailed Description
- Preuzima/Potvrđuje:** Person In Charge
- Procenjena vrednost bez PDV-a:** Estimated Value
- Plan realizacije projekta:** Project Reference
- Ostali zahtevi:** Additional Information
- Market Research Information:** (indicated by a callout box)

The form also displays a table of procurement items and a bar chart showing the distribution of procurement values.

Decision on Grounds for Exemption from Public Procurement Procedures

Metod nabavke
Metod nabavke...

Pozicija plana nabavke
Pozicija plana nabavke...

Izvor finansiranja
Odaberite izvor finansiranja...

Procurement Type (PPO)

Plan Reference (PPO)

Funding Source (FM)

Zahtev odobren, Vladimir Cmajerić, 13.11.2020, 13:44h

Nabavka odobrila, Bojan Gavrilović, 12.11.2020, 13:53h

Zahtev kompletiran, Marko Panić, 05.11.2020, 15:15h

Finansije odobrile, Katarina Petković, 06.11.2020, 10:24h

Nabavka dopunila zahtev, Bojan Gavrilović, 05.11.2020, 10:00h

Podnet zahtev, Marko Panić, 06.11.2020, 09:56h

Procurement Request

- Public Procurement Procedure
- Non-Public Procurement Procedure
- Call-off (Purchase Order) Procedure

If there are grounds for exemption, the Public Procurement Officer (PPO) indicates that the procurement method (procurement type) is non-public procurement – after which a choice of supplier / service provider is made by the unit or project manager based on the entered market research information. If the method is call-off, the contract manager in charge of the framework agreement needs to be informed prior to submission and continues the procedure as defined in the agreement after the request is signed off on. Finally, if the method is public procurement, the PPO prepares the tender documents for publication.

Procurement Procedure Implementation

Non-Public Procurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requester confirms the approval of the received offer or requests a binding offer from the approved supplier / service provider if needed to complete the transaction (pro-forma invoice, invoice, etc). Requester receives the goods / services / works and attaches invoices and supporting documents in the application (in communication with PPO and FM if needed).
Public Procurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PPO prepares the tender documents: decision on public procedure implementation and formation of a committee, solicitation document, other tender documentation, opens the received bids, evaluates them as part of committee and prepares a decision on award or procedure cancellation, prepares the contract or framework agreement and resolves procedural disputes by unsuccessful bidders Requester is by rule a member of the implementation committee for procurements over 3 million RSD without VAT and if the contract is signed, becomes the contract manager, receives the goods / services / works and attaches invoices and supporting documents in the application (in communication with PPO and FM if needed).
Call-off	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contract Manager prepares the purchase order or invites qualified suppliers to submit new bids for items not covered by the specifications in the framework agreement, opens the new bids, evaluates them and then creates the purchase order Contract Manager (assisted by Requester if needed) receives the goods / services / works and attaches invoices and supporting documents in the application (in communication with PPO and FM if needed).

Dynamic Purchasing Systems

A **Dynamic Purchasing System** is a **technique** utilized in qualifying suppliers and awarding **public** procurements, for cases when it is preferable to have a more flexible and longer term system of purchasing from several sources or in cases of non-fixed quantities are required, **instead of a classic contract with one supplier for a fixed quantity** for a particular subject matter of procurement. It is in that sense very similar to **Framework Agreement** as it represents an **option** and not an obligation for the buyer until a call-off is issued. The **call-off is an obligation for both the buyer and the supplier**.

The differences between a Framework Agreement (FA) and a Dynamic Purchasing System (DPS) are:

- A DPS is open for new suppliers throughout its duration, whereas a FA is closed for entry after it is set up
- A DPS can last longer than an FA (longer than 4 years)
- A DPS must be fully electronic, an FA does not
- Procedural complaints in a DPS do not halt the contract (call-off) award, whereas in an FA it does
- Competition for call-offs in a DPS must last a minimum of 10 days, while in a FA they can be shorter

DPS is usually combined with an electronic catalogue.

An **e-catalogue** is an **electronic itemized list** that the suppliers fill out by entering data (most importantly, **prices**) that the CA can then analyze to **buy on the basis of the item price** and not the total price of any one bidder's offer. This can be an alternative to lots since each item is now considered to be a separate lot.

Framework Agreements and Call-offs

Framework Agreement is a **technique** utilized in awarding **public** procurements, for cases when it is preferable to have a more flexible and longer term system of purchasing from several sources or in cases of non-fixed quantities are required, **instead of a classic contract with one supplier for a fixed quantity** for a particular subject matter of procurement. **FA** represents an **option** and not an obligation for the buyer until a call-off is issued. The **call-off is an obligation for both the buyer and the supplier**.

A framework agreement (FA) is signed **between one or more buyers and one or more suppliers**, following a **public** procurement procedure, in order to **set out how contracts or purchase orders (call-offs) will be awarded** to the suppliers which are party to the agreement, **as well as how the call-offs will be executed** particularly in terms of **prices and, if appropriate, quantities** of the goods, services or works, for the duration of the FA.

If an FA is with **only one supplier**, it also known as a **Framework Contract**, as it typically sets down all the terms and conditions as a typical contract, and **either fixes the price and not the quantity or the quantity and not the price** of goods, services or works.

If an FA is with **more than one supplier**, it is implemented in either of these three ways:

1. **Without opening up** call-offs for **competition** between the suppliers which are party to the agreement
2. **With opening up** call-offs for **competition** between the suppliers which are party to the agreement
3. **With partially opening up** call-offs for competition and **partially awarding call-offs without competition** between the suppliers which are party to the agreement

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Awarding Call-offs in Framework Agreements

Awarding Call-offs in DPS

FA's and Call-offs at BioSense

FA's with only one supplier

Travel Arrangements - bookings

- duration: until December 2022;
- supplier: Top Travel Center TTC and MAJA limo service;
- Call-offs: dedicated email address for booking, the emails constitute purchase orders
- Manager: Ivana Omazić

Since this is a Framework Contract no Procurement Request is needed, as there is no competition, and the prices are fixed for the duration of the FA.

FA's with more than one supplier

Lab consumables and auxiliary materials

- duration: until August 2023;
- suppliers: RTC, Uni-chem, Proanalytica, Novos, KEFO, Main Solution;
- Call-offs: partially fixed prices – direct award for certain items, and mini tenders for items not on the price lists in the FA.
- Manager: Jovana Stanojev

The Requester should first check with the Contract Manager if the items they require are already on the itemized lists and the prices for which are fixed based on the bids for awarding the FA.

If they are, the Requester submits one or more requests in the application (grouped by supplier), depending on how many suppliers cover the items (one supplier per request - for all the items from that supplier).

If the required items are not on the list, the Contract Manager organizes a mini tender offline to get bids from the suppliers in the FA. When these new bids are received, the Requester submits the requests in the application, the same way as for the items that were on the lists (one request for each supplier with the winning items for that supplier).

If the mini tender yields no valid new bids for the items not on the lists, the Requester submits a request for these items as they would for any other procurement (the results of the request will then not be a call-off and the suppliers will not be those party to the FA).

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DPS and Call-offs at BioSense

DPS

Computers and computer equipment

- duration: until December 2024;
- suppliers: currently JAPI COM, AS COMPUTERS & TECHNOLOGY, KING ICT, but open for new entrants in the DPS;
- Call-offs: NO fixed prices – mini tenders every time a call-off is required.
- Manager: Goran Kitić

The Requester should first check with the Contract Manager if the items they require are already on the itemized lists.

If they are, the Requester submits a request in the application - for all the item and the PPO organizes a mini tender through the government Portal.

If the required items are not on the list, the Contract Manager and PPO update the list on the government Portal before any mini tenders can be used for call-offs.

If the mini tender yields no valid new bids for the items in the Purchase Request, the Requester submits a request for these items as they would for any other procurement (the results of the request will then not be a call-off and the suppliers may be other than those in the DPS).

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Value Thresholds for Exemptions from Public Procurement

Subject-matter	Threshold (Serbia)	EU Threshold
Goods and Services	1,000,000 RSD w/o VAT	€214,000 w/o VAT
Social and Other Specific Services	15,000,000 RSD w/o VAT	€750,000 w/o VAT
Works	3,000,000 RSD w/o VAT	€5,350,000 w/o VAT
Small Lots for Goods and Services	300,000 RSD w/o VAT	€80,000 w/o VAT
Small Lots for Works	500,000 RSD w/o VAT	€1,000,000 w/o VAT

If the procurement estimated at less than the Serbian value threshold annually, Procurement Principles apply, but not a Public Procedure. Instead, the BioSense Rulebook on Procurement applies, which states that you need at least one bid for procurements under 100,000 RSD without VAT, a more than one bid for procurements valued between 100,000 and 999,999 RSD without VAT.

If the procurement is equal to or above the Serbian threshold, then public procurement rules apply (a tendering procedure is necessary).

An international tendering procedure is necessary if the procurement is valued at being equal to or above the European threshold, which means longer bid submission times.

Small lots are an option for exemption if a public procurement is divided into several lots. If that is the case, the CA may exempt the lots valued at less than the amount given in the table above, but only for those lots which when summed up do not go over the regular threshold for exemption. (eg. In an open tendering procedure for services, which is divided into lots, those lots that are individually estimated at less than 300,000 RSD without VAT, but when summed up do not go over the 1,000,000 RSD without VAT, can be exempt from the public procurement procedure.

Exemptions for Research and Development

The Serbian Public Procurement Act has an exemption for procurement of R&D services in line with the EU Directive:

Public Procurement Act (2019)

Član 12

Odredbe ovog zakona naručioc **ne primenjuju na:**
 12) **usluge** istraživanja i razvoja, **izuzev** kada su predmet javne nabavke usluge istraživanja i razvoja koje su obuhvaćene CPV oznakama od 73000000-2 do 73120000-9, 73300000-5, 73420000-2 i 73430000-5 **ukoliko** su ispunjena **oba** sledeća uslova:

(1) **korist ostvaruje isključivo naručilac**, odnosno namenjene su isključivo njegovoj upotrebi i obavljanju njegovih poslova i

(2) naručilac **u celosti finansira** te usluge.

EU Directive 24/2014

Article 14

This Directive **shall only apply to** public service contracts for research and development services **which are covered by** CPV codes 73000000-2 to 73120000-9, 73300000-5, 73420000-2 and 73430000-5 **provided that both of the following conditions are fulfilled:**

(a) the **benefits accrue exclusively to the contracting authority** for its use in the conduct of its own affairs, and

(b) | the service provided is **wholly remunerated** by the contracting authority.

Exemptions for Research and Development

Општи речник набавке (CPV):

- 73000000-2 Услуге истраживања и развоја и пратеће саветодавне услуге
- 73100000-3 Услуге у области истраживања и експерименталног развоја
- 73110000-6 Услуге истраживања
- 73111000-3 Услуге истраживачких лабораторија
- 73112000-0 Услуге истраживања мора
- 73120000-9 Услуге експерименталног развоја
- 73300000-5 Планирање и спровођење истраживања и развоја
- 73420000-2 Прелиминарна студија изводљивости и технолошка презентација
- 73430000-5 Испитивање и оцењивање

Common Procurement Vocabulary (CPV):

- 73000000-2 Research and development services and related consultancy services
- 73100000-3 Research and experimental development services
- 73110000-6 Research services
- 73111000-3 Research laboratory services
- 73112000-0 Marine research services
- 73120000-9 Experimental development services
- 73300000-5 Design and execution of research and development
- 73420000-2 Pre-feasibility study and technological demonstration
- 73430000-5 Test and evaluation

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Procurement Planning Process Flows

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Procurement Planning – Annual Needs Assessment

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Procurement Needs Assessment Form

Type of Subject-matter (goods / services / works)
Subject-matter Description (what exactly is to be bought?)
Estimated Value (maximum payable amount) in RSD without VAT
Market Research Method (website, email RFI, previous contract information...)
Planning Unit (Planner) (Center / Department / Project or whole Institute)
Project Name (or proposal name if proposal was submitted but still not approved, OR "N/A" for units)
Contracting Latest Date (by which the contract or delivery must be initiated)
Planning Unit Manager (Planner) Name (for explanations and potential changes and updates)

This Form is an internal tool for procurement needs assessment. It should be filled in by Project or Unit Managers for individual units (centers and departments) and projects or submitted proposals.

Based on these individual lists, an Institute-level list is then compiled and checked against legal and financial requirements for planning (procurement and financial plans).

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Procurement Classification and Plan Drafting

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Public Procurement Plan

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Public Procurement Plan

Istraživačko-razvojni institut za informacione tehnologije biosistema

Rbr	Predmet javne nabavke	Vrsta predmeta	Procenjena vrednost	Vrsta postupka	Okvirno vreme pokretanja	Glavna CPV oznaka	NSTJ isporuke / izvršenja
0001	Analiza izotopa stroncijuma	Usluge	3.400.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	1. Kvartal	71900000	RS123
0002	Analiza radiokarbonskih datuma	Usluge	2.700.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	1. Kvartal	71900000	RS123
0003	Diferencijalni multiplexer	Dobra	1.200.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38000000	RS123
0004	Georadar	Dobra	21.600.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38220000	RS123
0005	Izrada veb-sajta	Usluge	1.200.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	1. Kvartal	72413000	RS123
0006	Komplet za udarno bušenje za heterogena zemljišta	Dobra	2.600.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38220000	RS123
0007	Laboratorijska oprema za projekat IPANEMA	Usluge	1.700.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38000000	RS123
0008	Laboratorijski zamrzivač	Dobra	2.000.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38000000	RS123
0009	Mikrofluidični kontroler sistem za regulaciju protoka	Dobra	3.000.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38000000	RS123
0010	Oprema za rad sa sisarskim ćelijama	Dobra	1.600.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38432000	RS123
0011	Usluge računovodstvene revizije po međunarodnim projektima	Usluge	1.700.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	79210000	RS123
0012	Serveri i serverska oprema	Dobra	1.600.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	1. Kvartal	48800000	RS123
0013	Sistem za doziranje kao nadogradnja za uređaj Anton Paar Litesizer	Dobra	4.000.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38000000	RS123
0014	Usluge sekvencioniranja	Usluge	1.200.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	71900000	RS123
0015	Usluge posredovanja pri obezbeđenju avio karata, smeštaja, prevoza i kotizacija na službenom putu	Usluge	50.000.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	4. Kvartal	63500000	RS123
0016	Najam vozila sa vozačem	Usluge	3.000.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	60170000	RS123
0017	Sistem za vakuumiranje	Dobra	1.500.000 RSD	Otvoreni postupak	2. Kvartal	38000000	RS123
			104.000.000,00				

Q&A

Thank you

Further Procurement Resources:

BioSense Resources

- [BioSense Rulebook on Procurement \(in Serbian\)](#)
- [BioSense #procurement Channel on chat.biosense.rs](#)
- [BioSense Instructions on Electronic Procurement Requests](#)
- [Webinar - Procurement Essentials and Procurement at BioSense](#)
- [BioSense Project Management System project.biosense.rs](#)
- [BioSense Public Procurement Webpage \(CA Profile\)](#)

Serbian Resources

- [Law on Public Procurement \(Serbia\)](#)
- [Rulebooks on Public Procurement \(Serbia\)](#)
- [Guidelines on Public Procurement \(Serbia\)](#)
- [Public Procurement Portal \(Serbia\)](#)
- [Public Procurement Office \(Serbia\)](#)
- [Republic Commission for Protection of Bidder Rights \(Serbia\)](#)

EU Resources

- [Public Procurement Notices in OJEU \(Tenders Electronic Daily\)](#)
- [EU Directives on Public Procurement](#)

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Figure 6 Screenshots from the Public Procurement workshop

3. Conclusion

One of the goals of the NANOFACTS project is to develop research management and administration (RMA) skills of participating researchers, in order to enable them to competitively participate in current and new research activities, secure new funding, generate results of the highest quality and publish them in high-impact peer-reviewed journals.

Therefore, this deliverable was written to summarize all the organized trainings and presentations concerning RMA skills in the period from the start of the project (Jan 1st 2021) until Dec 31st 2021.

All of the presented trainings and info-sessions were estimated as useful by our participating researchers who already started implementing what they learned in their current activities.

Lasting benefits are expected for the Institute in terms of research management methodology and progress in planning of specific research projects' activities. To that aim, the trainings on RMA skills will be continued in the next year of the NANOFACTS project.

4. Annex

4.1 Photos of BIOS researchers on the IEEE webinar & obtained certificates

4.2 Screenshots of the obtained certificates from IEEE webinar

4.3 Photo from the Info session on Horizon Results Booster showing our researcher participating

4.4 Photo from the Public procurement workshop

Public Procurement Plan

When new circumstances occur (a proposal gets financed, a new contract or agreement is signed, etc) that affect the plan, but were not included in the original planning stages, immediately notify the Public Procurement Officer and the Financial Manager to see if amendments should be made and if yes, to initiate a formal amendment procedure for the public procurement plan and / or the financial plan of the Institute.

When a public procurement plan for the year is set out and published, **if estimated value of any listed procurement needs to be increased by more than 10%, it is legally required to amend the published plan** through the process which is the same as for making the original plan.

Annual Procurement Planning Timeline	
By November 1	PPO sends Procurement Needs Form and instructions to planners
By November 20	Individual forms submitted by planners
By November 25	Institute-level list compiled, checked and reported back
By December 1	Individual planners review and update list if needed
By December 5	PPO sends institute level list to FM to draft financial plan
By December 10	FM drafts annual financial plan
By December 15	PPO drafts annual public procurement plan
By December 20	Financial and public procurement plan drafts sent to Institute Director
By December 25	Institute Director sends financial and public procurement plan drafts to Board
By December 31	Financial and Public Procurement Plan adopted by Board decision

Draft Plan Submission

Board Decision

Publishing

Periodic Review and Amendments

List of attendees:

